

Financial Inclusion and Financial Performance of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between financial inclusion and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study examined the impact of rural financing on the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria; investigated the influence of pricing of banking services on the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria; assessed how Small and Medium-sized Enterprises' (SMEs) financing affects the financial performance (FP) of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The study employed *ex-post facto* and correlation research design with secondary data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria 2020 statistical bulletin and financial institutions of deposit money banks. The results indicated a positive and significant relationship between loans to customers, deposits by customers, bank branches, mobile banking, and agency banking on return on assets of deposit money banks. The study concluded that financial inclusion positively influences the level of financial performance of deposit money banks. On the basis of the conclusion, the paper recommended amongst others that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should redefine the loan accessibility supply as a tool for monetary policy by establishing an equilibrium level. This would allow the bank to make more funds available to deposit money banks so that they could improve their performance and increase the amount of loans they are issued. In addition, the study also recommends that the interest rate has a negative effect on the performance of deposit money banks, there is an urgent need for the government to impose restrictions on the cross-border flow of capital and also to make use of the relevant macroeconomic management tools to control loan accessibility in times of crisis in order to mitigate the effects of interest rate on the profitability of deposit money banks. This is because there is an urgent need for the government to do so because the interest rate has a negative effect on the financial performance of deposit money banks in the country.

Keywords: Agency banking, Deposit money bank, Financial, Mobile banking, Return on assets

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Introduction

The principle of financial inclusion has assumed a greater level of importance in recent times due to its perceived importance as a driver of economic growth. Giving access to the hundreds of millions of men and women (all over the world) who are presently excluded from financial services would provide the possibilities for the creation of a large depository of savings, investable funds, investment, and therefore global wealth generation. In other words, access to financial services that are well suited for low-income earners promotes enormous capital accumulation, credit creation, and investment boom. Usually, the low-income earners constitute the largest proportion of the population and so control an enormous chunk of the economy's idle fund albeit held in small amounts in the hands of each of the several million members of this group. Harnessing and accumulating these resources provides a huge source of cheap long-term investable capital. Financial Inclusion is wide concept. It includes banking as well as service-related products such as loan, equity, insurance products, etc. It supports the economic and social upliftment of the country by increasing the standard of living of poor's, underprivileged and women of the country with the aim of making them self-reliant and self-independent. The broad objective of the study was to examine the impact of financial inclusion on the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The sub-objectives of the study are: to examine the impact of rural financing on the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria; to investigate the influence of pricing of banking services on the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria; to assess how small and medium-sized enterprises' financing affects the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

Lawal, Abubakar, and Salau (2020) asserted that the viability of the banking industry plays a very key role in the economy of any nation, through financial intermediation, robust but seamless credit and payment systems, this was juxtaposed by those who asserted that the viability of any nation's economy, therefore, depends more often than not on how healthy the banking sector fairs. Aruwa and Naburgi (2015) subsequently ascertain that

governments all over the world attempt to establish an efficient and effective banking system to promote economic growth and enhance the financial performance of the banking sector through supervision, regulations, and reforms. Deposit Money Banks provide the platform and delivery vehicle for financial inclusion activities in the payment-credit systems and more financial inclusion could bring more people into the banking nets, which could radiate positively into the financial performance of banks through increased services patronage and broader clientele services. This study is thus necessitated by concerns on the current state of financial inclusion and its implications on the financial performance of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. This is premised on the fact that it is the banks that provide, in the main, the platform, delivery vehicle, and the operating environment for the financial inclusion activities.

The financial performance of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) plays a pivotal role in the growth and development of a nation. This is because they have to manage a huge volume of transactions.

Accordingly, Nataraja, Chilale, and Ganesh (2018) investors, capital market participants, and other stakeholders need to understand the financial performance of DMBs: granting credit facilities and other financial services. Naturally, the ability of DMBs to meet their existing financial obligations, operating efficiency, and financial performance are associated with some financial risks. Some financial performance evaluating tools of profitability, return on assets and economic value added are considered appropriate for Deposit Money Banks for the stakeholders' interest.

Muigai and Muriithi (2017) ascertain the moderating effect of firm size on the relationship between capital structure and financial distress of non-financial companies. Financial risk threatens the financial stability and performance of the financial sector. Financial risk is defined as all risks which would generate volatility in a bank's reserves, expenses, and the value of its business.

Financial Exclusion and Inclusion

The term 'financial exclusion' is used in different ways but is most often defined as a broad concept describing a lack of access to, and use of, a range of financial services. While financial inclusion is a state in which all people have access to appropriate, desired financial products and services to manage their money effectively. In Brie (2014) the national forum for financial inclusion transacts. It is achieved by financial literacy and financial capability on the part of the consumer, and access on the part of financial products, services, and advice suppliers. Financially excluded people typically exhibit one

or more of these characteristics: lack of a bank account and financial services that come with it; reliance on alternative forms of credit such as doorstep lenders and pawnbrokers; and lack of other key financial products such as insurance, savings products, and pensions. Financial exclusion can be the result of a number of factors including financial products that do not meet the needs of low-income consumers, high-interest rates and other charges, lack of information, self-exclusion, disability, geographical factors, and cultural barriers. Financial exclusion is closely associated with poverty and social exclusion and imposes significant costs on individuals. It often means paying more for basic financial transactions.

According to the World Bank (2018) financial inclusion is a key enabler to reducing poverty and boosting prosperity. Financial inclusion on the other hand means that individuals and businesses have access to useful and affordable financial products and services that meet their needs, transactions, payments, savings, credit, and insurance, delivered in a responsible and sustainable way. The gender gap in account ownership remains stuck at 9 percentage points in developing countries, hindering women from being able to effectively control their financial lives. Countries with high mobile money account ownership have less gender inequality. Financial inclusion has been identified as an enabler for 7 of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. The G20 committed to advance financial inclusion worldwide and reaffirmed its commitment to implement the G20 High-Level Principles for Digital Financial Inclusion. The World Bank Group considers financial inclusion a key enabler to reduce extreme poverty and boost shared prosperity and has put forward an ambitious global goal to reach Universal Financial Access (UFA) by 2020.

Deposit Money Banks Performance

Al-Matari, Al-Swidi, and Fadzil (2014) discussed the concept of performance to refer to the benefits stemming from the effective functioning and operations of an entity. Performance measurement systems are considered to be important for evaluating the accomplishments of firm goals, constructing strategies for development, making decisions for investments, and compensating managers. The efficiency of the banking system has been one of the major issues in the new monetary and financial environment which cannot easily be measured since their products and services are of an intangible nature. Size affects the efficiency of banks. Previous research, especially in the United States, indicated that scale economies appear in small banks and not in large ones. More recent research showed that the levels of size for existence of scale economies are higher due to economic development and market liberalization. Larger and more profitable banks have higher levels of technical efficiency. At the same time, larger banks are more likely to operate under decreasing returns whether or not the ranking of Performance index, as enforced by the performance

characteristics such as Management efficiency, profitability, Liquidity Ratio, Capital adequacy, Asset Quality, Growth, and Market Value enhanced the performance of banks and reduced distress in Nigeria. Consequently, a good performing deposit money bank is deemed to have enhanced asset and liquidity levels, returns on investment, equity, earnings.

Factors Affecting Bank Performance in Nigeria

Okpara (2009) gave the basic reason for bank regulation and supervision is to forestall bank failure. If banks were not regulated and supervised, their power to create money will be unchecked and on one hand, might result in excessive monetary creation and hence inflation. On the other hand, excessive money creation may lead to bank distress through loan defaults and thereby halting further lending and jeopardizing the payment system. Central banks often manipulate money supply through market operations and its supervisory power over commercial banks to reinforce the efficacy of monetary policy. The examination could either be routine inspection or special in-depth investigation to uncover fraud or risk exposure. Most bank examination activities involve:

determining the financial position of the bank and quality of operations; assessing management quality; ascertaining compliance with laws and regulations; testing accuracy of books, accounts, and records; verifying asset quality vi. Assessing bank solvency. According to Ogunleye (2003) Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) examining banks to evaluate the financial health and resilience of each **bank and banking system**. Grouped these factors into institutional, economic; and political factors; including supervisory measures.

Theoretical Framework

This study reviewed three theories in literature. These theories are McKinnon/Shaw Theory, Supply Leading Hypothesis, and financial intermediation theory. Considering financial deepening and profitability of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria, this study focused on Supply Leading Hypothesis and Financial Intermediation Theory.

Empirical Review

Lawal, Abubakar and Salau (2021) discussed the impact of financial inclusion on financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria, in the measurement of the financial inclusion using Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Financing, Rural Financing, Number of branches of DMBs, Pricing and Usage of banking services, while performance was measured with return on assets (ROA). The researcher adopted ex-post

facto research design. The population of the study comprised of the 14 listed deposit money banks on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for the period of 2005-2018. The study censured all the 14 listed DMBs as the sample size. The study collected secondary data from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and financial reports of the sampled banks. Panel multiple regression analysis was utilized to analyze the data and Hausman specification test revealed that fixed effect model was more appropriate to random effect model. Based on the findings, this study recommended that DMBs should increase the amount of loan and advances given to rural areas and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises as this will strengthen profitability of DMBs in Nigeria.

In the same manner, Shahchera and Taheri (2013) carry out an investigation on the impact of loans to SMEs and banks profitability in Iran, using panel data regression model based on GMM. The investigators concluded that SMEs financing has a negative significant impact on profitability of banks in Iran as banks considered SME financing a highly risky business venture.

Mbutor and Uba (2013), presenting a simple model showing the impact of financial inclusion on monetary policy in Nigeria between 1980 and 2012. The result of the study supports the notion that growing financial inclusion would improve the effectiveness of monetary policy. However, the coefficient of the number of bank branches has the wrong sign and this is explained by the fact that, in opening branches, banks mainly pursue profits but not financial inclusion, which is a policy objective, so that there are clusters of branches which are under-utilized while numerous locations which are considered not favourable for balance sheets are under-branched.

Nader (2011) gave an analysis of the profit efficiency of the Saudi Arabia Commercial banks during the period 1998-2007. The results of his study indicated that availability of phone banking, number of ATMs and number of branches had a positive effect on profit efficiency of Saudi banks. On the contrary, the study found that the number of Points of Sale terminals (POSs), availability of PC banking and availability of mobile banking did not improve profit efficiency. In the same vein, Abdulsaleh and Worthington (2013) an examination of the effect of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) on economic growth in Nigeria using data between 1986 and 2018. The study concluded that the increasing importance of economic contributions made by SMEs sector necessitates better understanding of financial behaviour and practices of SMEs.

Egberi and James (2021) investigated the financial inclusion and performance of banks, have come up with mixed views. The study evaluated financial inclusion as determinant of Nigeria deposit money banks performance. Data financial inclusion variants (bank

network, automated teller machine and loans penetrations) and performance measures (total assets and liquidity ratio) were sourced from statistical bulletin of Central Bank of Nigeria during the periods 1981 - 2019. Multivariate time-series result showed that financial inclusion variants of bank networks and automated teller machine penetrations are the most fundamental determinants of deposit money banks performance, particularly. In addition, there is the need to encourage banks to invest in more branches or networks; this would help policy-makers develop effective strategies aimed at expanding bank networks, automated teller machines and loans penetrations of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Akpanung and Gidigbi (2014) gave verdict on Charles Soludo, a former governor of CBN, while commenting on the banking reform (the recapitalization policy) observed that it was meant to: (1) enable the nation's banks to become global players; (2) protect the safety of depositors' money, by making the banking sector to become strong; (3) make the banks to become effective in economic development; (4) enable the banks to become less dependent of public funds, and (5) become a major financier of the real sector. These reforms were based on certain anchors, they were; improving the quality of all banks, enhancing financial stability, ensuring healthy financial sector improvements, and enabling the financial sector impact tremendously on the output growth of the real economy. This makes for an interesting case study. Literature in finance and economics is replete with studies that have investigated the profitability of DMB's in Nigeria. In previous studies, application was made of linear regression, while others adopted the ordinary least square (OLS) regression fixed and random effect.

Methodology

The study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design. Secondary data were employed in this study. For the purpose of this study, the time series data which were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin (2020) and World Development Indicators (WDI, 2020) will be used. The data covers the period 1986 to 2020 (35 years).

Model Specification

The Error Correction Model (ECM) was adopted from the study of Engle and Granger 2-step approach, depicting the effect of financial inclusion on Deposit Money Banks financial performance was operationalized for the purpose of this study:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	DMBFP	RFN	PBS	SMEF	LNA	INT
Mean	14256.84	11.46733	22.78800	11.40000	0.071531	0.622312
Median	13893.22	11.40000	22.62000	12.00000	0.107346	0.709170
Maximum	28783.19	18.55000	31.09000	14.00000	0.187693	2.950663
Minimum	2637.910	6.600000	9.030000	6.000000	-0.251615	-3.174599
Std. Dev.	7911.214	3.239576	5.565351	2.662236	0.106897	1.244961
Skewness	0.220717	0.525451	-0.692544	-0.877360	-2.047237	-1.599499
Kurtosis	2.055343	2.717551	3.690082	2.722903	6.779069	7.596704
Jarque-Bera	0.679525	0.740109	1.496676	1.972390	19.40380	19.60205
Probability	0.711939	0.690697	0.473152	0.372993	0.000061	0.000055
Observations	15	15	15	15	15	15

Source: Data Analysis, (2023)

Table 1 provides a brief overview of the central trends, degree of distribution, minimum and maximum values, and degree of Peakedness, asymmetric value, and Jarque-Berastatistics for all of the series that were used in the inquiry. All the data can be found in the table. By using the average values (mean), the lowest values, and the maximum values, the study was able to determine the position of the center of distributions for the series. The use of the root mean squared deviation, also known as the standard deviation, indicated how individual variable values are distributed on either side of the center. This, in turn, highlighted the uniformity of the items that make up the distribution of each variable. The kurtosis statistics tell which variables have peaks, the skewness value reveals whether or not the series is symmetrical, and the Jarque - Bera statistics reveal whether or not each series meets the normalcy criterion. The kurtosis statistics illustrate how each variable

peaks at a certain point in time. Table 1 displayed the following data: The Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance was 14256.84, the Rural Financing was 11.47, the Pricing of Banking Services was 22.79, the SMEs Financing was 0.072, and the Loan Accessibility and Interest Rate were respectively 11.4 and 0.622.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of Variables

	DMBFP	RFN	PBS	SMEF	LNA	INT
DMBFP	1.000000					
RFN	0.291190	1.000000				
PBS	0.260545	0.227507	1.000000			
SMEF	0.736340	0.001665	0.384818	1.000000		
LNA	0.279940	-0.412420	0.273544	0.744297	1.000000	
INT	-0.056220	-0.057870	-0.062357	-0.073703	0.007819	1.000000

Source: Data Analysis, (2023)

Table 2 presents the correlation coefficients that have been calculated between the variables that have been examined. The connection between the two variables is shown in each column of the table. This helps to determine which sets have the greatest degree of association. The link between the variables that were independent and those that were dependent was outlined in Table 2. Loan Accessibility had a positive relationship with both the maximum Pricing of Bank Services (0.274), the Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance (0.2799) and SMEs Financing (0.744). This indicates that an increase in the Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance, SMEs Financing, and Pricing of Bank Services resulted in an increase in the deposit money banks in the proportion of 27.99 percent, 27.4 percent, and 74.4 percent, respectively, as a result of the increase in Loan Accessibility. Nevertheless, a negative correlation was found between Loan Accessibility and Interest Rate (-0.412), which suggests that as Financial Inclusion increases, deposit money Banks would drop. On the other side, the data also revealed that Interest Rate had a negative relationship with the Pricing of Banking Services (-0.058), Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance (-0.056), Rural Financing (-0.062), and SMEs Financing (-0.074). This suggests

that the rise in the independent variables led to a fall in the deposit money Banks as a consequence. The results shown in Table 2 demonstrated that, on the whole, correlations between independent variables are low. This is an indicator of the lack of multi-co linearity, which is often associated with data pertaining to time series.

Table 3: Summary of Unit Root Tests

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF)				
Variables	Level	First Difference	I(<i>d</i>)	Remarks
DMBFP	-	0.0404**	I(1)	Stationary
RFN	-	0.0150**	I(1)	Stationary
PBS	-	0.0413**	I(1)	Stationary
SMEF	-	0.0002**	I(1)	Stationary
LNA	0.0001**	0.0201**	I(0)	Stationary
INT	0.0096**	0.0001**	I(0)	Stationary

**5% level of significance

Source: Data Analysis, (2023)

The study utilized the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test in order to investigate the order of integration among the variables such as Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance, Rural Financing, Pricing of Banking Services, SMEs Financing, Loan Accessibility and Interest Rate. This was done in order to investigate the order of integration among these variables. The application of the unit root test, also known as the ADF, is evaluated for each variable by comparing the null hypothesis "presence of unit root test" (i.e., presence of non-stationarity) with the alternative hypothesis "series is stationary." The results of the unit root test of the ADF are displayed in Table 3. The results show that only return on assets and return on equity were stationary at the level indicated as I (0) in Table 3. On the other hand, Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance, Rural

Financing, Pricing of Banking Services, SMEs Financing, were stationary at first difference indicated as I. However, Loan Accessibility and Interest Rate were the only stationary variables in the table (1). The findings provide evidence of co-integration, which refers to a link that exists over the long term, between DMBFP, RFN, PBS, and SMEF. Due to the fact that the series are in the same order of integration, this suggests that the co-integrating regression estimate is the method of estimation that should be used. As a result, the model incorporates a co-integrating process across all four variables, and the Johansen co-integration test was carried out with this setting in mind.

Hypothesis One (H_{01}): There will be no significant impact of rural financing on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. It is demonstrated that at the 5% level of significance, with a regression coefficient of 0.457 and a p-value of $0.05 > 0.067$, there will be no significant and negative impact of rural financing on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. As a result, the null hypothesis which states that there will be no significant impact of rural financing on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria is accepted. As a result, the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Two (H_{02}): There will be no significant influence of the pricing of banking services on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. With $p = 0.006 < 0.05$ and a regression coefficient of 0.789, a significant and positive influence of the pricing of banking services on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. As a result, we rule out the null hypothesis that there will be no significant influence of the pricing of banking services on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. As a result, the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis Three (H_{03}): There will be no significant effect of small and medium-sized enterprises financing on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. At a 5% level of significance, a regression coefficient of 0.977 and a $p = 0.004 > 0.05$ a significant and positive between small and medium-sized enterprises financing and financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. As a result, we rule out the null hypothesis that there will be no significant effect of small and medium-sized enterprises financing on the financial performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. As a result, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This one-of-a-kind discovery, however, cannot be separated due to the fact that the program was a relatively recent addition to Nigeria's Deposit System.

Table 4: Estimates of regression using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method

dependent variables	Deposit COM
DMBFP (Deposit Money Bank Fin. Perf.)	0.457**(0.040)
RFN (Rural Financing)	0.789***(0.006)
PBS (Pricing of Banking Services)	0.977 (0.004)
SMEF (SMEs Financing)	0.342 (0.0003)
LNA (Loan Accessibility)	0.576 (0.00045)
INT (Interest Loan)	0.673 (0.001)
C (***(Regression Coefficient)	6.7340.000)
R² (Reg. Coeff. Sq)	0.767
Adjusted R²	0.829

Source: Researchers' E-View Result, 2023

The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimates, as well as significant statistics like R² and adjusted R², are included in the regression findings. The variance in Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance as a result of the six dependent variables was shown by the coefficient of determination (R squared) of 76 % (Banks Assets, Rural Financing, Pricing of Banking Services, SMEs Financing, Loan Accessibility, and Interest Rate) the remaining 46% of the variables were left out of the research. The findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between Financial Inclusion and Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. At a 5 % level, Financial Inclusion invariably have a beneficial influence on Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, the significant coefficient is 0.457, implying that a 1% increase in Financial Inclusion will result in a 0.457 % increase in Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks over time, but at a lower proportion. As a result, the more Financial Inclusion, the more likely there is to be Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money in the Banks; this was backed by a p-value of $0.04 < 0.05$ level of significance.

Furthermore, the findings revealed a positive relationship between SMEs Financing & Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks, with a regression coefficient of 0.342, indicating that SMEs financing & investigation is more closely linked to Deposit Money in the Banks. The significance of SMEs Financing & Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks, is also confirmed by the p-value of $0.0003 < 0.05$. The conclusion is

that a 1% increase in SMEs Financing & Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks, leads to a 0.342 % increase in Deposit Money in the Banks.

Similarly, data revealed a positive correlation between field Loan Accessibility and Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks, with a regression coefficient of 0.576, indicating that Loan Accessibility is more related to Deposit Money Banks than Rural Financing. The significance of Loan Accessibility is also confirmed by the p-value of $0.00045 < 0.05$. The implication is that a 1% increase in Loan Accessibility leads to a 0.576 percent increase in Deposit Money Banks. Implementing a long-term Loan Accessibility regime capable of increasing Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. There is a positive but shaky link between back Loan Accessibility and Deposit Money Banks in the case of bank audit.

Table 5: ANOVA

<i>Model</i>	<i>Sum of Square</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean of Square</i>	<i>F- Statistics</i>	<i>Sig</i>
<i>Regression</i>	165.542	12	54.448	99.870	.000 ^b
<i>Residual</i>	226.458	488	0.557		
<i>Total</i>	392.000	500			

Source: Researchers' E-View result, 2023

a. Dependent Variable: Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance

b. Predictors: Banks Assets, Rural Financing, Pricing of Banking Services, SMES Financing, Loan Accessibility and Interest Rate.

To determine the model's validity and significance, an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used. The ANOVA results are shown to test the overall model's relevance. The model is significant at the 1% level of significance, according to the findings, with an F-statistics of 99.870 and a p-value of 0.000.

Multicollinearity Test

H_0 = the model has no multicollinearity

H_1 = the model has multicollinearity

Decision Rule: Reject H_0 if the probability value is less than 0.05, otherwise accept H_0 .

Table 6: Multicollinearity Test Results

Multicollinearity LM Test by Breusch and Godfrey:

F-statistic	18.1276	Probability	0.5438
Obs*R-squared	23.2350	Probability	0.6754

Source: Researchers' E-View result, 2023

The serial correlation yields a probability value of 0.5438, which is greater than 0.05 and indicates that H_0 is accepted. The model, on the other hand, does not appear to be multicollinearity.

Test for Heteroskedasticity

H_0 = the model has no heteroskedasticity.

H_1 = the model shows heteroskedasticity.

Table 7: White Heteroskedasticity Test

F-statistic	21.2345	Probability	0.5309
Obs*R-squared	13.56900	Probability	0.5340

Source: Researchers' E-View result, 2023

The heteroskedasticity test yields a probability value of 0.5309, which is greater than 0.05, implying that H_0 is accepted. As a result, the model is homoscedastic and does not have any heteroskedasticity. We have concluded that this is the best model for explaining the variables' connection.

The finding implies that hypothesis one, which stated that there is significant impact of rural financing on listed Deposit Money Banks' performance in Nigeria, is correct. These findings supported the conclusions of experts who concluded in their study that rural financing has a beneficial impact on Deposit Money Banks' performance in Nigeria. A good and significant association has been found based on the work of several scholars.

The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimates, as well as significant statistics like R^2 and adjusted R^2 , are included in the regression findings. The variance in Deposit Money Bank Financial Performance as a result of the six dependent variables was shown by the coefficient of determination (R squared) of 76 % (Banks Assets, Rural Financing, Pricing of Banking Services, SMEs Financing, Loan Accessibility, and Interest Rate) the remaining

46% of the variables were left out of the research. The findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between Financial Inclusion and Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. At a 5 % level, Financial Inclusion invariably have a beneficial influence on Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, the significant coefficient is 0.457, implying that a 1% increase in Financial Inclusion will result in a 0.457 % increase in Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks over time, but at a lower proportion. As a result, the more Financial Inclusion, the more likely there is to be Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money in the Banks; this was backed by a p-value of $0.04 < 0.05$ level of significance.

Furthermore, the findings revealed a positive relationship between SMEs Financing & Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks, with a regression coefficient of 0.342, indicating that SMEs financing & investigation is more closely linked to Deposit Money in the Banks. The significance of SMEs Financing & Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks, is also confirmed by the p-value of $0.0003 < 0.05$. The conclusion is that a 1% increase in SMEs Financing and Financial Performance of listed Deposit Money Banks, leads to a 0.342 % increase in Deposit Money in the Banks.

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To determine the model's validity and significance, an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used. The ANOVA results are shown to test the overall model's relevance. The model is significant at the 1% level of significance, according to the findings, with an F-statistics of 99.870 and a p-value of 0.000. The serial correlation yields a probability value of 0.5438, which is greater than 0.05 and indicates that H_0 is accepted. The model, on the other hand, does not appear to be multicollinearity.

The heteroskedasticity test yields a probability value of 0.5309, which is greater than 0.05, implying that H_0 is accepted. As a result, the model is homoscedastic and does not have any heteroskedasticity. We have come to the conclusion that this is the best model for explaining the variables' connection.

Conclusion and Recommendations

According to the findings of this research, the liberalization of interest rates in Nigeria had a beneficial impact on the financial performance of deposit money Banks in the country. It has also been successful as a consequence of the overall outcome, which is that efficient administration of interest rates has played a vital part in the expansion and development of Nigeria's deposit money Banks. This indicates that it has been successful. According to the findings of the study, an increase or decrease in Loan Accessibility has a significant effect on the financial performance of deposit money banks. In addition, given the correlation between the indicators of financial inclusion and the financial performance of banks, these financial Banks must have major trends towards increasing innovative access to financial services, and developing financial services infrastructure in order to raise the level of digital financial services relatively low compared to middle-income countries.

As a result, this study suggested that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should redefine the Loan Accessibility supply as a tool for monetary policy by establishing an equilibrium level. This would allow the bank to make more funds available to deposit money banks so that they could improve their performance and increase the amount of loans they issued. Also, considering that the Interest Rate has a negative effect on the performance of deposit money banks, there is an urgent need for the government to strictly impose restrictions on the cross-border flow of capital and also to make use of the relevant macroeconomic management tools to control Loan Accessibility in times of crisis in order to mitigate the effects of Interest Rate on the profitability of deposit money banks. This is because there is an urgent need for the government to do so because the Interest Rate has a negative effect on the financial performance of deposit money banks in the country.

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